

CHILDHOOD AS A SOCIAL PHENOMENON

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Annotation.

The article examines the essence of the process of socialization of children as a non-disciplinary field of study (philosophy, psychology, pedagogy, sociology).

It is argued that socialization is a two-way process, where the importance of the social environment (language, values, culture, norms of behavior) and the active position of the individual himself, taking into account his age and individual characteristics, are important.

The article reveals the influence of globalization, the media, the Internet and innovation on the socialization of children.

Key words: childhood, socializing personality, sociocultural space, children's culture, social relations, transformation, small culture, large culture, children's culture, sociohistorical environment, world of childhood.

From a philosophical point of view, human childhood can be considered as a social phenomenon in its characteristics. Childhood is a kind of initial period of a person's life, it is a period that is formed in social conditions, that is, in society, it is a logical phenomenon, on the one hand, and a social phenomenon, on the other. When a person is born as a biological being, from the moment of birth he gradually enters into the process of socialization, as he begins to live in society.

Childhood appears as a unique social reality, a small society within a society, a small culture within a large culture, characterized by the young person's entry into public life, the assimilation of its laws and rules, that is, socialization. Because every person experiencing childhood is influenced by the social relationships that have developed in society from the moment of birth, for example, parents, doctors and other social persons who provide services to him and enter his life. It is known that these individuals are formed in society and, based on the necessary skills, experience and knowledge collected there, influence the child and begin to participate in the process of his upbringing. As a result, the child, a socializing personality, finds himself in a new sociocultural space where people like him live. This process represents that a young child is formed under the influence of existing rules in a specific sociocultural world, changes and assimilates them. Since this new world is "new" for the child, it appears in his mind as indelible, vivid events. In his consciousness, on the one hand, the features of the same social space, characteristic of all children, are formed, and on the other hand, elements of culture that arise on the basis of his individuality, which belongs only to him.

In childhood studies, a distinction is made between "adult culture" and "children's culture," formed as an individual that has emerged in modern times. In fact, dividing the culture of a society and a nation into such types of culture as "adult culture", "youth culture" or "children's culture" is inappropriate from a scientific-theoretical point of view and

methodologically. However, based on the purpose and subject of the research, the mentioned types of culture are distinguished. Their commonality lies in the fact that they were formed in the same social and cultural space, and their specificity is associated with the specific features of society and culture that are characteristic of different young people.

Of course, in a certain sense this is the right approach, because the world of children is different from the world of adults, and the process of their socialization is also different. Because the formation of the sociocultural world of children is related to their age, psychology, interests and needs. Accordingly, a “children’s culture” specific to children is formed in society. The same opinion can be said about the youth group.

If we turn to the history of Eastern philosophy, we can say that the study of the problem of childhood was studied mainly in the context of raising a child.

In European philosophy, childhood as a social phenomenon began to be studied much later. The French historian F. Ares pointed out that even in the field of art, insufficient attention was paid to the problem of childhood¹.

Famous scientists B. Malinovsky, M. Mead, R.F. Yor, Y. Hogbin, D. Whiting, who were classic representatives of social anthropology of the last century, who conducted extensive research in the field of studying childhood, focused on the early period of childhood based on the study of traditions and life of different peoples, who studied the following elements of this period: features of feeding (feeding) children; wrapping up children; alternation of hours of sleep and wakefulness in children; children's activity time; the formation of a personal attitude towards them in childhood; “child-child” and “child-adult” relationships between children; punish and reward the boy, etc. According to the anthropologists mentioned above, in some cultures children are not punished at all, while in others they continue to be punished until almost 20 years of age.

Russian scientist V.V. Avramenkova draws attention to the relationships between children, the formation of their “work collective,” relationships in children’s groups, and children’s folklore. At the same time, the scientist focuses on studying the role and significance of play in the lives of children, as well as the technology of play. In the study of the problem of childhood and children, the activities of the Research Institute of Ethnology and Anthropology named after N. N. Miklouho-Maclay, created as part of the Academy of Sciences of the Russian Federation at the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century, acquires great importance.

Scientific and theoretical research into such issues as the passage of childhood, the socialization of children, their needs, the contradictory influence of social problems on the consciousness of children in our country remains an important problem even for teachers, psychologists and philosophers of Uzbekistan.

The study of childhood from a socio-philosophical point of view requires that childhood is a social phenomenon, a historical phenomenon, that the socialization of a person from childhood, his interaction with the socio-historical environment, his formation as an individual, childhood is a unique socio-historical environment. -historical period. Childhood means that a person acts in social existence as the bearer and creator of various social events and processes occurring in him. This process proceeds as a unique complex system in the “universe-man” and “man-universe” relations. In it a person becomes a social person. Accordingly, the study of a specific stage in the process of personality formation - childhood in

the context of social existence, society and the complex and diverse social relations that arise in it - is an important philosophical problem.

An analysis of the world, social existence and the social relations manifested in it in relation to the phenomenon of childhood necessarily assumes that social existence influences, shapes and changes a person. The implementation of this objective process develops from simple to complex and covers human life. The revelation of human nature, the acquisition of life skills and experience by him occurs in three spheres: biological, social and personal. "The social and psychological changes that occur in childhood show that the potential of an adult exists even in childhood, that he is a moral and spiritual being is the state of the future person." Events associated with a person's entry into adolescence after childhood occur within the framework of various relationships that arise in society. Because from infancy a person enters into these "ready-made" relationships and exists in them, lives on the basis of these relationships, influences them and brings news. As a result, a person is not only a bearer of social relations, i.e. a simple subject living under their influence, but also their creator, i.e. an active creative person who introduces novelties and changes into the system of relations and improves them. Such an active person creates himself and also creates fixed social relationships.

Childhood has its own world, which is now served by a huge infrastructure. Kindergartens, various intellectual and sports centers, books, magazines, works of art created for children, cartoons, films, telephones, shopping centers, playgrounds, parks, cafes, etc. are involved in organizing and influencing the lives of children. The expansion and development of such infrastructure will certainly have a positive and sometimes negative impact on childhood. On their basis, a unique landscape of the child's "world of childhood" is formed. The culture of childhood is formed in accordance with this landscape.

Currently, children's culture is undergoing a strong transformation under the influence of globalization, media, the Internet and innovation. These events can negatively affect the formation of the child's psyche, thinking and intellectual potential. As a result, various contradictory trends are reflected in childhood and determine the characteristics of the formation of the child as an individual. It is in this area that the modern characteristics of children's works of art change, and their characters and plots "play their role." Based on the social system and national traditions, rules, values, which play an important role in the socialization of the child and his entry into adulthood, they must be brought up in the national spirit and become patriots and patriotic citizens of society and society. For this, an important task is to develop mechanisms for protecting the nation and nationalism from strong transformation.

Childhood can be defined as follows: childhood is the initial socialization period of a person's life, lasting from birth to adulthood and characterized by the creation of the basis for his self-expression as a full-fledged subject of society. According to the famous psychologist L. S. Vygotsky, it is incorrect to talk about childhood in general terms. Childhood, as a historical and cultural phenomenon, should be discussed in harmony with the history of society. In conclusion, we can say: childhood is a unique period of socialization of a person's life, in which the fundamental foundations of a person's development as an individual are formed

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